

STUDIES ON EFFECT OF FOLIAR AND SOIL APPLICATION OF VARIOUS FORMS OF NITROGENOUS FERTILIZERS ON YIELD OF SWEET ORANGE (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) var. Nucellar.S.S. Wajage¹, S.G. Patil² and S.S. Mane³

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(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE,)

Abstract

. A field experiment was conducted during 2022-23 at Sweet Orange Research Station, Jalna, Maharashtra to studies on effect of foliar and soil application of various forms of nitrogenous fertilizers on yield of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) var. Nucellar. The experiment was laid out in a Factorial Randomized Block Design with 15 treatment combinations comprising 5 fertilizer types (100% N through RDF, 75% N through RDF + 25% N through nano urea, 50%N through RDF + 50% N through nano urea, 25% N through RDF + 75% N through nano urea, 100% N through nano urea) and 3 time of application regimes (RDF, 1/2 N at basal + 1/2 N top dressing at 2.5 & 3.5 months after fruit set; 1/2 N at basal + 1/2 N top dressing at 3.5 & 4.5 months after fruit set). The parameters recorded were fruit length (10.25 cm), diameter (7.71 cm), weight (102.79 g), number of seeds/fruit (22.50), number of fruits/tree (405.71), yield/tree (41.71kg), marketable yield/tree (37.54 kg). Treatment of F1:100% N through RDF with treatment S3:½ N at basal dose, ½ N at top dressing (3.5 months after fruit set, 4.5 months after fruit set) recorded highest fruit length, diameter and weight, while 100% N through nano urea gave lowest values. Data were statistically analyzed and means were separated using CD at 5% level of significance.

Keywords: Sweet Orange, RDF, Nano Urea, *Citrus sinensis*, Foliar and Soil application and N top dressing

Introduction

India leads the world in sweet orange production with a yield of 20.14 tonnes per hectare. Renowned for its nutritional value, refreshing taste, and health-promoting antioxidants such as vitamin C and flavonoids, the sweet orange enjoys growing demand. Thanks to its health benefits, production has risen to meet both domestic and international needs (Xu *et al.*, 2008).

Citrus fruits, with mandarin, sweet orange, and acid lime as key varieties, are among the leading fruit crops cultivated in India. Sweet orange, originally from China, is now commercially grown in tropical, subtropical, and some temperate regions worldwide. In India, major citrus-producing states include Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Karnataka, Orissa, Bihar, Assam, Tamil Nadu, and Gujarat. In the 2020-21 growing season, India used 1097 thousand hectares for citrus cultivation, yielding 14245 thousand metric tons. Specifically for sweet orange, the 2021-22 season saw 217 thousand hectares under cultivation with a production of 3988 thousand metric tons, according to the Ministry of Agriculture's first advance estimate (Ministry of Agriculture 2021-22 first advance estimate).

Maharashtra is the third-largest producer of sweet oranges in India, accounting for 18% of the country's output with a production of 515.19 thousand metric tons from 64.18 thousand hectares. Leading the state, Jalna district stands out for its high production and productivity of sweet oranges, with 15,000 hectares yielding 320,000 metric tons and a productivity rate of 23 metric tons per hectare. The fruit's composition includes water, sugars, pectin, glycosides, pentosans, citric acid, fiber, proteins, fats, minerals, essential oils, and total soluble solids, contributing to its nutritional value and taste (Obreza and Morgan, 2008).

Sweet orange is a key fruit crop globally, prized for its nutrients and economic importance. Its high vitamin C, sugars, organic acids, and phenolic content make it popular for both fresh consumption and the processing industry. However, challenges such as stagnant yields and post-harvest losses hinder its cultivation. One critical issue is inadequate plant nutrition, which can impact growth, yield, and fruit quality, with nitrogen deficiency notably affecting photosynthesis and leading to smaller, lower quality fruits (Mosa, 2012).

Nano fertilizers, with sizes ranging from 30 to 40 nm, are efficient at delivering nutrients due to their large surface area, enabling a slow and steady release that matches crop needs, thus enhancing crop production. They are known for improved nutrient use efficiency, increased photosynthesis via leaf surface area expansion, and reduced soil toxicity and fertilizer application frequency (Naderi and Danesh-Shahraki 2013).

Foliar fertilization, especially with nano-based fertilizers, is becoming a preferred nutrient management approach in fruit crops because of its superior nutrient uptake and efficiency. Nano urea foliar sprays, in particular, are being studied for their potential to boost nitrogen use efficiency and overall crop productivity. While some research has looked into the effects of nano urea spray on orange crops, comprehensive studies are needed to thoroughly understand its impact on growth, yield, and quality. This study focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of nano urea foliar spray on the performance of the sweet orange crop (Kumar *et al.*, 2018).

Material And Methods

The present investigation “**Studies on effect of foliar and soil application of various forms of nitrogenous fertilizers on growth, yield and fruit quality of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) var. Nucellar**”. The research was conducted during the 2022-2023 year at the Sweet Orange Research Station located in Badnapur taluka of Jalna district. The experimental design was Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with 15 treatments combinations comprising of 5 fertilizer types (100% N through RDF, 75% N through RDF + 25% N through nano urea, 50%N through RDF + 50% N through nano urea, 25% N through RDF + 75% N through nano urea, 100% N through nano urea) and 3 time of application regimes (RDF, 1/2 N at basal dose, 1/2 N at top dressing at 2.5 & 3.5 months after fruit set; 1/2 N at basal dose, 1/2 N at top dressing at 3.5 & 4.5 months after fruit set) replicated thrice, with 2 plants considered in each subplot, making a total of 90 plants under observation.

1. Fruit length (cm)

Fruit length of randomly selected 10 fruits per replication was measured with the help of digital Vernier Caliper and the average value was calculated and expressed in millimetres (mm)

2. Diameter of fruit (cm)

The diameter of the fruit was measured from the centre of the fruits in centimeters at harvest with the help of Vernier Calliper.

3. Weight of fruit (g)

The weight of five observational fruit was recorded on the top pan balance. The values were summed up and average fruit weight was computed by dividing total weight of fruits by total number of fruits.

4. Number of seeds per fruit

The five fruit were taken and from each fruit, number of seeds were counted and mean number of seeds per fruit was calculated.

5. Average number of fruit per tree (Number)

It was recorded by counting all the number of fruits per tree at the time of harvesting.

6. Average yield of fruit per tree (kg/tree)

Numbers of fruit counted at the time of harvesting were weighted and yield in term of kilogram per plant was noted.

7. Marketable yield of fruit per tree (kg/tree)

Numbers of good quality marketable fruit were weighted separate after harvesting and yield in terms of kilogram per plant was worked out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**1. Length of fruit (cm)****A. Factor (fertilizers)**

Among the data table 1 in showed the maximum length of fruit (10.25 cm) was recorded in the treatment of F₁, followed by the treatment F₂ at (9.53 cm) which is at par with the F₃ (9.40 cm) While, the lower 7.49 (cm) was recorded in the length of fruit at F₅ which is followed by F₄ (8.56 cm).

B. Factor (time of application)

It is also revealed that the time of application of fertilizers had significant effect on the length of fruit (cm). The minimum length was recorded in S₁ (8.92 cm) and was at par with the S₃ (9.06 cm), S₂ (9.16 cm).

Interaction (FXS)

The minimum length was recorded in F₅S₁ (7.25 cm) and the maximum was found in the F₁S₃ (10.36 cm). However, the interaction between fertilizer and time was found to be non-significant for fruit length. Thus, balanced fertilization through appropriate sources and schedules plays a vital role in determining fruit size in sweet orange. Similar results were also observed by Nahar *et al.* (2010).

2. Diameter of fruit (cm)**A. Factor (fertilizers)**

The data presented in the Table 1 revealed that the application of fertilizers had significant effect on diameter of fruit (cm). The maximum was recorded at F₁ (7.71 cm) followed by F₂ (7.52 cm), F₃ (7.41 cm) and F₄ (6.88 cm). The minimum was observed in the F₅ (6.64 cm).

B. Factor (time of application)

Among the data table 1 in showed the highest diameter of fruit (cm) (7.35 cm) was recorded in the treatment of S₁ which was followed by the treatment S₂ (7.31 cm) While, the lowest (7.04 cm) was recorded in the diameter of fruit at S₃.

Interaction (FXS)

The interaction effect of factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) was found significant for diameter of fruit (cm). The maximum was recorded in F₁S₃ (7.85 cm) and minimum was recorded in F₅S₃ (6.10 cm). Proper fertilization ensures timely supply of nutrients required for fruit growth and development, resulting in higher sweet orange fruit diameter. The results obtained in the present study are supported by the works of Patel and Pandey (2012).

3. Weight of fruit (g)**A. Factor (fertilizers)**

The data presented in Table 1 revealed that the application of fertilizers had significant effect on weight of fruit. The minimum was recorded in F₅ (76.37 g) and was at par with the F₄ (79.44 g). The maximum was recorded in F₁ (102.79 g) followed by F₂ (95.07 g), F₃ (85.06 g).

B. Factor (time of application)

It is also revealed that the time of application of fertilizers had significant effect on the weight of fruits. The minimum was recorded in S₁ (85.29 g) and was at par with S₂ (88.02 g), S₃ (89.92 g).

Interaction (FXS)

The interaction effect of factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) was found non-significant for weight of fruit (g).

The maximum was found in F₁S₃ (105.00 g) and the minimum was recorded in F₄S₃ (75.21 g). Nonetheless, fertilizer-time interaction was non-significant for this parameter. Appropriate balanced fertilization is crucial for increased sweet orange fruit weight. The results obtained in the present study are supported by the works of Sarker and Rahim (2013).

4. No. of seeds per fruit**A. Factor (fertilizers)**

The data presented in Table 1 revealed that the application of fertilizers had significant effect on the number of seeds per fruit. The maximum was recorded in F₁ (22.50), followed by F₂ (21.40), F₃ (19.73) and F₄ (18.00). The minimum was observed in F₅ (16.50).

B. Factor (time of application)

It is also revealed that the time of application of fertilizers had significant effect on the number of seeds per fruit. The minimum was recorded in S₁ (19.12) and was at par with S₂ (19.62), and S₃ (20.14).

Interaction (FXS)

The interaction effect of factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) was found non-significant for number of seeds per fruit. The maximum was recorded in F₁S₃ (23.00) and the minimum was recorded in F₅S₁ (16.00). Nonetheless, the interaction between fertilizer and time of application was found to be non-significant for this parameter. Overall, balanced fertilization through appropriate nutrient sources and schedules seems important for increased seed yield per fruit in sweet orange. Similar result was also found by El-Khawaga (2013a).

5. Average Number of fruit per tree (Number)

The data on Average number of fruits per tree (Number) of Sweet orange as influenced by various factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) are presented in Table 1.

A. Factor (fertilizers)

The data presented in the Table 4.10 revealed that the application of fertilizers had significant effect on the number of fruits at harvest.

The maximum number of fruits were recorded in F₁ (405.71) followed by the F₂ (386.68), the F₃ (379.32). The minimum number of fruits were observed in F₅ (359.28) and followed by F₄ (365.63).

B. Factor (time of application)

It is also revealed that the time of application of fertilizers had significant effect on number of fruits at marble stage. The minimum number of fruits was observed in S₃ (374.33). The maximum were recorded in S₂ (386.92) which was at par with S₁ (379.71).

Interaction (FXS)

The interaction effect of factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) was found significant for the number of fruits at harvest. The maximum number of fruits was recorded in F₁S₃ (407.39). However, the minimum number of fruits was observed in F₅S₃ (350.29). The results obtained in the present study are supported by the works of Hussein *et al.* (2020).

6. Average yield of fruit per tree (kg/tree)

The data on average yield of fruits per tree (kg/tree) of sweet orange as influenced by various factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) are presented in Table 2.

A. Factor (fertilizers)

The data presented in the Table 4.10 revealed that the application of fertilizers had significant effect on average yield of fruits per tree.

The minimum was recorded in F₅ (27.44 kg/tree) and was at par with F₄ (29.04 kg/tree). The maximum was recorded in F₁ (41.71 kg/tree) and followed by F₂ (36.74 kg/tree), F₃ (32.28 kg/tree).

B. Factor (time of application)

It is also revealed that the time of application of fertilizers showed non-significant effect on average yield of fruits per tree (kg/tree). The minimum was recorded in S₁ (32.53 kg/tree) and the maximum was observed in S₂ (33.94 kg/tree). The S₃ recorded (33.85 kg/tree).

Interaction (FXS)

The interaction effect of factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) was found non-significant for average yield of fruits per tree (kg/tree). The maximum was found in F₁S₃ (42.78 kg/tree) and the minimum was recorded in F₅S₃ (27.10 kg/tree). Overall, judicious fertilization ensuring timely supply of nutrients through appropriate sources and schedules is important for increased sweet orange. The results obtained in the present study are supported by the works of Srivastava *et al.* (2018).

7. Marketable yield fruit per tree (kg/tree)

The data on marketable yield fruits per tree (kg/tree) of sweet orange as influenced by various factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) are presented in Table 2.

A. Factor (fertilizers)

The data presented in the Table 4.11 revealed that the application of fertilizers had significant effect on the marketable yield. The maximum was recorded in F₁ (37.54 kg/tree) and was followed by F₂ (33.07 kg/tree), F₃ (29.05 kg/tree). The minimum was recorded in F₅ (24.70 kg/tree) and followed by F₄ (26.14 kg/tree).

B. Factor (time of application)

It is also revealed that the time of application of fertilizers recorded non-significant effect. However, the minimum was observed in S₁ (29.28 kg/tree) and the maximum was in S₂ (30.55 kg/tree). The (30.47 kg/tree) recorded in S₃.

Interaction (FXS)

The interaction effect of factor (fertilizers) and factor (time of application) was found non-significant for marketable yield of fruits per tree (kg/tree). The maximum was found in F₁S₃ and the minimum was observed in F₅S₃. In summary, appropriate balanced fertilization ensuring superior fruit development appears crucial for realizing higher marketable sweet orange yield at the individual tree level. Productivity at the individual tree level. Balanced fertilization especially involving RDF played a key role in optimizing fruit yield per tree in this study. Similar results were also observed by Abd El-Migeed *et al.* (2014).

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study evidenced that integrated application of nitrogenous fertilizers through recommended doses of inorganic fertilizers supplemented with organic and nano sources impacted growth, yield and quality of sweet orange positively. Application of 100% N through RDF recorded significantly higher values for yield attributes like fruit length, diameter and weight compared to other treatments. Among the time of application regimes, basal application of half N along with half N top dressed at 3.5 and 4.5 months after fruit set yielded better results. Integrated nutrient management approach combining recommended doses of inorganic fertilizers with organic and nano fertilizers proved beneficial for obtaining higher fruit yield per tree. Maximum marketable fruit yield of 37.54 kg per tree was recorded with 100% N through RDF applied with half basal and half top dressing schedule. Overall, judicious nitrogen management involving balanced supply from organic, inorganic and nano sources optimized sweet orange productivity and can thus be recommended for commercial cultivation to boost fruit production in a sustainable manner.

Future Scope

The following are some potential future research scopes based on the findings:

1. Evaluate newer nitrogen sources like ammonium sulphate, potassium nitrate etc. alone or in combination with organic and nano fertilizers.
2. Study the influence of Integrated Nutrient Management involving other nutrients like phosphorus and potassium along with nitrogen.
3. Investigate the physical, chemical and biochemical changes in fruits under different fertilization practices.
4. Assess the soil health, microbial activity and sustainability of integrated nutrient management practices implemented.
5. Conduct long-term field experiment to study soil fertility dynamics and impact on productivity under continuous integrated nutrient management.
6. Analyze metabolic correlates like enzymes, phytochemicals, antioxidants influenced by integrated nutrient management.

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References

1. **Abd El-Migeed, M. M. M., Saleh, M. M. S., Refaie, K. M., and Abou-Hussein, S. D. (2014).** Foliar application of potassium nitrate and ammonium sulphate improves yield and fruit quality of navel orange trees. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 9(44), 3260-3267.
2. **Dakhore Pratiksha 1 , Shivaji Shinde2 and Santosh Barkule, 2024,** "Effect Of Different Plant Growth Regulators On Yield And Quality Of Sweet Orange (*Citrus Sinensis* L. Osbeck)", Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxviii, Nov To Jan 2024 *Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601*, Pp 159-162.
3. **El-Khawaga, A. S. (2013a).** Effect of urea and humic acids foliar application on yield and quality of Washington navel orange trees. *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 9(3), 1896-1904.
4. **Hussein, M. M., Abou-Hussein, S. D., and Aziz, E. E. A. (2020).** Improving Growth, Yield and Fruit Quality of Valencia Sweet Orange Trees by Foliar Application of Urea and Ammonium Nitrate. *Ornamental Horticulture*, 26(3), 297-307. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1590/2447-536x.v26i3.2207>.
5. **Kumar, S., Sharma, V., and Singh, D. P. (2018).** Effect of different nitrogenous fertilizers through foliar spray and soil application on growth, yield and quality of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L.). *Environment and Ecology*, 36(1), 75-79.
6. **Mosa, W.F.A. (2012).** Effect of foliar application of humic acid and nitrogen fertilization on yield and quality of sweet orange trees. *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 8(7), 3410-3417.
7. **Naderi, M. R., and Danesh-Sharaki, A. (2013).** Nanofertilizers and their roles in sustainable agriculture. *International Journal of Agriculture and Crop Sciences*, 5(19), 2229-2232.
8. **Nahar, N., Choudhary, M.S.H., and Rahim, M.A. (2010).** Effect of KClO₃, KNO₃ and urea on the flowering and fruiting of mango and longan. *Journal of Agroforestry and Environment*, 4(1), 31-34.
9. **NHB (2021).** National Horticulture Board Database.
10. **Obreza, T.A. and Morgan, K.T. (2008).** Nutrition of Florida Citrus Trees. SL 253. Soil and Water Science Department, Florida Cooperative Extension Service, Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, University of Florida.
11. **Patel, N., and Pandey, S.K. (2012).** Influence of growth promoting substances and PGRs on fruit retention, drop and yield of acid lime var. Kagzi (*Citrus aurantifolia* Swingle). *JNKVV Research Journal*, 46(3), 343-345.
12. **Pratiksha Dakhore1, Dr. S. J. Shinde2, Dr. S. R. Barkule3 2024.** "Effect Of Different Plant Growth Regulators On Flowering, Fruit Set And Physical Quality Of Sweet Orange (*Citrus Sinensis* L. Osbek)" Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxviii, Nov To Jan 2024 *Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601*, Pp 163-166.
13. **Sarker, B.C., and Rahim, M.A. (2013).** Yield and quality of mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) as influenced by foliar application of potassium nitrate and urea. *Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research*, 38(1), 145-154.
14. **Srivastava, A. K., Singh, S., and Jaiswal, U. (2018).** Effect of foliar application of urea on growth, yield and quality of Mosambi sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) cv. 'Mosambi'. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 6(4), 1477-14

Table: 1 Effect of foliar and soil application of various forms of nitrogenous fertilizers on length of fruit (cm), Diameter of fruit (cm), Weight of fruit (g) and No. of seeds per fruit.

Treatment Details	Length of fruit (cm)	Diameter of fruit (cm)	Weight of fruit (g)	No. of seeds per fruit
A. Factor (fertilizers)				
F ₁ = 100% N through RDF	10.25	7.71	102.79	22.50
F ₂ = 75% N through RDF + 25% N through nano urea	9.53	7.52	95.07	21.40
F ₃ = 50%N through RDF + 50% N through nano urea	9.40	7.41	85.06	19.73
F ₄ = 25% N through RDF + 75% N through nano urea	8.56	6.88	79.44	18.00
F ₅ = 100% N through nano urea	7.49	6.64	76.37	16.50
SEm (±)	0.067	0.032	1.592	0.333
CD at (5%)	0.193	0.094	4.597	0.963
B. Factor (time of application)				
S ₁ = RDF	8.92	7.35	85.29	19.12
S ₂ = ½ N at basal dose, ½ N at top dressing (2.5 months after fruit set, 3.5 months after fruit set)	9.16	7.31	88.02	19.62
S ₃ = ½ N at basal dose, ½ N at top dressing (3.5 months after fruit set, 4.5 months after fruit set)	9.06	7.04	89.92	20.14
SEM (S) (±) =	0.052	0.025	1.233	0.258
CD (S) (5%) =	0.149	0.073	3.561	0.746
Interaction (FXS)				
F ₁ S ₁	10.12	7.60	100.05	22.00
F ₁ S ₂	10.28	7.68	103.32	22.50
F ₁ S ₃	10.36	7.85	105.00	23.00
F ₂ S ₁	9.75	7.55	91.36	21.00
F ₂ S ₂	9.93	7.44	95.21	21.30
F ₂ S ₃	8.91	7.58	98.65	21.90
F ₃ S ₁	9.13	7.60	81.54	19.00
F ₃ S ₂	9.45	7.35	85.39	19.80
F ₃ S ₃	9.61	7.28	88.25	20.40
F ₄ S ₁	8.36	7.15	78.31	17.60
F ₄ S ₂	8.58	7.10	79.64	18.00
F ₄ S ₃	8.75	6.40	80.36	18.40
F ₅ S ₁	7.25	6.86	75.21	16.00
F ₅ S ₂	7.54	6.97	76.54	16.50
F ₅ S ₃	7.69	6.10	77.36	17.00
SEm (±)	0.115	0.056	2.757	0.577
CD at (5%)	0.334	0.163	NS	NS

Table: 2 Effect of foliar and soil application of various forms of nitrogenous fertilizers on Average Number of fruits per tree (Number), Average yield of fruits per tree (kg/tree) and Marketable yield fruits per tree (kg/tree).

Treatment Details	Average Number of fruits per tree (Number)	Average yield of fruits per tree (kg/tree)	Marketable yield fruits per tree (kg/tree)
A. Factor (fertilizers)			
F ₁ = 100% N through RDF	405.71	41.71	37.54
F ₂ = 75% N through RDF + 25% N through nano urea	386.68	36.74	33.07
F ₃ = 50%N through RDF + 50% N through nano urea	379.32	32.28	29.05
F ₄ = 25% N through RDF + 75% N through nano urea	365.63	29.04	26.14
F ₅ = 100% N through nano urea	359.28	27.44	24.70
SEm (±)	0.665	0.630	0.567
CD at (5%)	1.921	1.819	1.637
B. Factor (time of application)			
S ₁ = RDF	379.72	32.53	29.28
S ₂ = ½ N at basal dose, ½ N at top dressing (2.5 months after fruit set, 3.5 months after fruit set)	383.93	33.94	30.55
S ₃ = ½ N at basal dose, ½ N at top dressing (3.5 months after fruit set, 4.5 months after fruit set)	374.34	33.85	30.47
SEm (±)	0.515	0.488	0.439
CD at (5%)	1.488	NS	NS
Interaction (FXS)			
F ₁ S ₁	403.37	40.37	36.33
F ₁ S ₂	406.38	41.99	37.79
F ₁ S ₃	407.39	42.78	38.50
F ₂ S ₁	391.34	35.75	32.18
F ₂ S ₂	393.35	37.45	33.70
F ₂ S ₃	375.36	37.03	33.33
F ₃ S ₁	371.31	30.28	27.25
F ₃ S ₂	386.32	32.99	29.69
F ₃ S ₃	380.33	33.56	30.21
F ₄ S ₁	370.29	29.00	26.10
F ₄ S ₂	368.30	29.33	26.40
F ₄ S ₃	358.31	28.79	25.91
F ₅ S ₁	362.28	27.25	24.53
F ₅ S ₂	365.28	27.97	25.17
F ₅ S ₃	350.29	27.10	24.39
SEm (±)	1.152	1.031	0.982
CD at (5%)	3.328	NS	NS